

Polarography of 6-Methyl-4-styrylcoumarin

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Polarography of coumarins and their uses in complexometric studies have been carried out by many workers¹. Orlov and Lichino² determined the molecular weight of natural coumarin polarographically. Polievktov and Lomadze³ studied by polarography some isocoumarins and found that in anhydrous DMF and in 50% ethanol, isocoumarin is reduced with more difficulty than the corresponding coumarins. Orlov⁴ carried out the determination of coumarin in sweet clover herbage by a polarographic method. No literature is available on the polarography of a styrylcoumarin and hence the present investigation on 6-methyl-4-styrylcoumarin was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

DC polarograms exhibited two waves (Fig. 1) and ac polarograms two peaks with constant current from pH 5.0 to 11.0. At pH 4.0 only one wave was seen. Average wave-slopes were 0.047 V and 0.058 V for the two waves. The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots were straight-lines with slopes 0.054 V (SCE) and 0.039 V (SCE)

Fig. 1. DC Polarograms of 6-methyl-4-styrylcoumarin (0.2 mmol dm⁻³) at 298 K.

TABLE 1— CONSTANT POTENTIAL COULOMETRY (298 K) OF 6-METHYL-4-STYRYLCOUMARIN (8×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³)

mole 2.0×10^{-6} , mF 0.193 C,		pH 9.0 Applied potential -1.40 V (SCE)		
i_d (μ A)	Q (C)	Q (mF)	n	
0.160	—	—		
0.090	0.180	0.932		
0.048	0.315	1.632	2.3	
0.300	0.395	2.050		

per pH-unit respectively. CV voltammograms did not exhibit any anodic peak (Fig. 2). The i_p vs $V^{1/2}$ plot was a straight-line passing through the origin and the current function $i_p/V^{1/2}$ was independent of scan-rate, indicating uncomplicated charge transfer process. The value of αn_a estimated at pH 11.0 was nearly unity.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 6-methyl-4-styrylcoumarin (0.1 mmol dm⁻³) at 298 K.

The coulometric analysis showed that the electroreduction occurred with the consumption of two electrons per molecule at pH 9.0 (Table 1). Constant potential electrolysis (pH 9.0) at -1.4 V on a 40 ml solution (1.0 mM) was followed by extraction of the products after making the solution slightly alkaline and its uv-spectra showed that $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ group of the styryl moiety was reduced to $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$. It was confirmed

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TABLE 2 – COMPARATIVE HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS

pH	Styrylcoumarin		2'-Hydroxychalkone		Coumarin $-E_{1/2}/V$ (SCE)	Cinnamic acid $-E_{1/2}/V$ (SCE)
	$-E_{1/2}/V$ (SCE)		$-E_{1/2}/V$ (SCE)			
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)		
5.0	0.965	1.15	0.775	0.915		
6.0						1.6
7.0	1.07	1.33	0.865	1.075	1.51	1.6
8.0					1.53	1.6
9.0	1.08	1.36	0.945	0.11	1.53	
10.0					1.53	
11.0	1.18	1.43	1.10	1.45	1.53	

by the disappearance of an ir band⁵ at about 1600 cm^{-1} .

To confirm further which of the groups in 6-methyl-4-styrylcoumarin was reduced, dc polarograms of 2'-hydroxychalkone, coumarin and cinnamic acid were recorded under the same conditions as for the depolariser and by observing the behaviour of all the three reference compounds (Table 2) ($E_{1/2}$, $E_{1/2}$ vs pH slope) it was concluded that 6-methyl-4-styrylcoumarin behaved as an α,β -unsaturated ketone of the chalkone type.

Mechanism for the electrode-process proposed is presented in Scheme 1.

Experimental

The test solution contained 0.2 mmol depolariser, 0.05 M acetic acid or glycine buffers, 0.005% gelatin and 50% aqueous methanol. Polarograms ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) for deaerated solutions were recorded using a Bruker

Scheme 1.

E 310 polarograph in conjunction with a Hewlett-Packard 7040 X-Y recorder. Capillary used had characteristics : $m = 1.312\text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 4.1\text{ s}$ at 70 cm height of Hg reservoir and controlled drop-time of 2 s was used for recording the polarograms. The pH-values of buffer solutions were checked with an Elico LI-120 pH meter (accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit).

Studies were conducted using various techniques, viz. DC, AC, CV in addition to cpc and cpe. A digital coulometer (model 640, Electrosynthesis Co., U.S.A.) was used for the CPC studies. For CPE, a locally made 5V, 3A potentiostat-galvanostat was used and the extent of electrolysis was monitored from time to time by recording polarograms with a dme already fitted into the cell. Products of electrolysis were identified by uv and ir spectra.

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